

Fabrication Cycle Influence on the Acoustic Emission Response of GFRP Composites

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ABSTRACT

On the basis of results obtained from preceding tensile testing and microscopic examination of GFRP composites with different fibre orientation and cure cycle, an acoustic emission (AE) testing technique was employed to detect structural variations induced into the material by different fabrication cycles. The AE response was recorded during the testing of tensile specimens and its patterns have been correlated to the structural information provided by available micrographs. It is shown that AE patterns can discriminate, with sufficient reliability, between different structure dependent properties determined by intentional cure cycle variations. These results suggest the possibility of detecting accidental non conformities to the fabrication cycle specifications of GFRP components.

INTRODUCTION

Results obtained from preceding tensile testing of prepreg GFRP composites fabricated with different fibre orientations and cure cycles have shown that simple tensile tests are not able to identify structural variations induced in laminates by cure cycle alterations (1). To this purpose more profound analyses were required as, for example, microscopic examinations (2). The latter succeeded in evidencing meaningful differences in porosity content that could be correlated to cure cycle characteristic parameters. This kind of examination, though, on one hand is time consuming and requires specialized personnel and on the other does not produce information on the resin gel state or fibre-matrix interface properties.

The need was felt by the authors to resort to a testing technique that could be at the same time simple, real-time and sufficiently sensitive to material variations.

Acoustic emission (AE) technique, as is generally recognized (3) (4), can detect with high sensitivity signals coming from the different fracture modes operating in composites and, at least in some cases, allow for their discrimination (5) (6).

Cure cycle	Orientation	Starting temperature (°C)	Starting pressure (MPa)	Heating rate (°C/min)	Time to reach cure temperature (min)	Cure temperature (°C)	Pressure Increase		Cure pressure (MPa)	Permanence at cure temperature (min)	Cooling
							Time (min)	Temperature (°C)			
I	0° ±45°	20	0.25	2.1	50	125	50	125	0.75	75	slow
II	0° ±45°	20	0.25	7.5	14	125	14	125	0.75	60	fast
IV	±45°	20	0.15	7.5	14	125	34	125	0.75	60	fast
V	±45°	20	0	7.5	14	125	--	--	0	60	fast

Tab. I - Cure cycle parameters.

MATERIAL

The material used for laminate fabrication was the same Crowfoot Satin glass fabric/isophthalic polyester resin prepreg utilized in (1) and (2). Two types of symmetric and equilibrated laminates, obtained by superimposing 8 prepreg laminae, were fabricated: the first with warp (90% of reinforcement) oriented in the 0° direction and the second with warp in the ±45° direction. For the reason of this choice see (1).

Fig. 1 - Cure cycles temperature and pressure versus time.

tensile samples, according to ASTM D 3039, were obtained from each laminate for AE detection during tensile testing.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental equipment comprises an Instron Universal Testing Machine (200 kN), an AE detection system and various recording instruments.

The Instron Machine was employed to tensile load the specimens at a displacement rate of 1 mm/min kept the same for all tests.

AE signals were detected by a piezoelectric resonant transducer (Brüel&Kjaer

In the present paper the authors intend to confront the problem of discriminating, through AE detection during simple tensile tests, structural alterations due to intentional cure cycle variations on the assumption that these inevitably influence the composite fracture behaviour.

Four different cure cycles were used, whose parameters (temperature - time - pressure) are in tab. I. In fig. 1 schematical graphs of temperature and pressure versus time are shown. More details on the adopted cure cycle are in (1).

One or two ±45° laminates were fabricated for each cure cycle, whereas two 0° laminates were fabricated only for the first two cure cycles. Six to ten

4344 - 70 kHz). The transducer was held on the specimen with adhesive tape and acoustically coupled with an ultrasonic couplant. Transducer output was preamplified by 40 dB and band-pass filtered (cut-off freq. 50 - 200 kHz). Preamplified signals were then fed to an AE modular instrumentation system (SEPEMA 4500). AE instrumentation was set up for all tests with 72 dB total amplification and 1.2 V threshold level.

For each test stress, ring-down total count (N_{ta}) and event count rate (\dot{N}_e) were contemporarily recorded as functions of time. Event total counts (N_{te}) were calculated through graphical integration of the recorded AE diagrams.

RESULTS

Graphs reported in figs. 2-8 display AE parameters, N_{ta} and \dot{N}_e , and stress, σ , as functions of time. In tab. II mean values of all test parameters are summarized. Void contents measured through microscopic examinations are also reported. 0° specimens

AE graphs and results are similar for specimens from laminates fabricated with the same cure cycle; thus for each "cure cycle" only one graph is reported.

Cure cycle I (fig. 2). Starting of AE activity is observed at about 25% of ultimate strength (u.s.). High intensity bursts are observed starting from 36% u.s. and

Cure cycle	Orientation	Activity initiation (% of u.s.)	Burst activity initiation (% of u.s.)	Relative maximum (% of u.s.)	$N_{te} \times 10^{-3}$	$N_{La} \times 10^{-3}$	$N_{te} / N_{La} \times 100$	$N_{te} / \sigma_{ult} (c/Nmm^{-2})$	$N_{La} / \sigma_{ult} (c/Nmm^{-2})$	Ultimate strength (N/mm ²)	Young modulus (N/mm ²)	knee stress (% of u.s.)	Porosity
I	0°	25	36	-	11	40	28	16	57	703	43460	-	2.3
II	0°	34	-	63	8	15	53	11	21	721	45560	-	0.5
I	+45°	39	67	81	70 *	140 *	50 *	461 *	921 *	152	17860	63	2.7
					22 **	45 **	50 **	145 **	296 **				
II	+45°	61	-	-	43	57	75	281	373	153	18370	61	0.6
IV	+45°	42	-	75	75	111	68	481	712	156	16500	60	4.4
V	+45°	55	-	-	48	120	40	600	1500	80	10670	87	26.0

* first group; ** second group

Tab. II - Summary of experimental results average values.

Fig. 2 - AE response from cure cycle I / 0° laminates.

Fig. 3 - AE response from cure cycle II / 0° laminates.

are superimposed to a low background activity. The latter does not increase as the test proceeds. Ring-down total counts at failure are 40×10^3 and event total counts 11×10^3 . The ratio N_{te}/N_{ta} is 28%.

Cure cycle II (fig. 3). AE activity starts at about 34% of u.s. and gradually increases up to 63% of u.s. where it shows a relative maximum; then it decreases slightly before increasing again in a steady manner up the final failure. During the whole test burst activity is not observed. Ring-down total counts are 15×10^3 , event total counts are 8×10^3 , N_{te}/N_{ta} is about 53%.

$\pm 45^\circ$ specimens

AE graphs and results are generally comparable for specimens from laminates cured with the same cycle, with the only exception of cure cycle I laminates where two different AE patterns, having about the same probability of occurrence, can be identified. Thus for cure cycle I two typical graphs are shown, whereas for all the other cure cycles only one graph is reported.

Fig. 4 - AE response from cure cycle I / $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates: first group

Fig. 5 - AE response from cure cycle I / $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates: second group

Cure cycle I (figs. 4 and 5).

The first signs of AE activity are recorded at 39% of u.s., i.e. significantly before the typical "knee" ($\underline{1}$) of the stress-time graph that occurs at about 63% of u.s.. Immediately after the knee (i.e. at about 67% of u.s.) a burst activity superimposed on an increasing background activity is noticed. The latter reaches a relative maximum at about 81% of u.s..

Global activity has not always the same intensity: among the 18 tested samples, two groups of 10 and 8 samples respectively can be identified, the first (fig. 4) with higher background and burst activities and the second with lower background and burst activities (fig. 5). For the first group: $N_{ta} = 140 \times 10^3$, $N_{te} = 70 \times 10^3$ and $N_{te}/N_{ta} = 50\%$. For the second group: $N_{ta} = 45 \times 10^3$, $N_{te} = 22 \times 10^3$, and $N_{te}/N_{ta} = 50\%$. For both groups an increase in

Fig. 6 - AE response from cure cycle II / $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates.

average activity is observed near the final failure.

Cure cycle II (fig. 6)

AE activity starts at about 61% of u.s. practically in coincidence with knee stress (1) (61% of u.s.). Background activity is conspicuous, no bursts are noticed and the global activity increases notably just before the final failure. N_{ta} mean value is 57×10^3 , N_{te} is 43×10^3 , and the ratio $N_{te}/N_{ta} = 75\%$

Fig. 7 - AE response from cure cycle IV / $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates.

Cure cycle IV* (fig. 7)

AE activity begins at about 42% of u.s., i.e. in advance with respect to knee stress (60% of u.s.). Burst activity is absent and background activity is conspicuous and increasing up to a very pronounced relative maximum (75% of u.s.). AE activity exhibits a slight increase just before the final failure. N_{ta} is 111×10^3 , N_{te} is 75×10^3 , and N_{te}/N_{ta} is 68%.

Cure cycle V (fig. 8). The first signs of AE activity are noticed rather late (55% of u.s.) only because in these samples the u.s. is particularly low. If AE initiation stress is compared with knee stress (87% of u.s.), it becomes evident that also in this case AE activity starts before knee stress value. Burst activity is not present and background activity is very high and continuously increasing, as the test proceeds, up to final failure. N_{ta} is 120×10^3 , N_{te} is 48×10^3 and N_{te}/N_{ta} is 40%.

ANALYSIS

From tab. II it can be seen that there are no meaningful differences in the mechanical tensile properties of 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ samples cured with different cycles with the only exception of cure cycle V. On the other hand microscopic examinations evidence marked differences in porosity content that can be correlated to

(*) Ordinals IV and V are used for authors' convenience instead of III and IV.

Fig. 8 - AE response from cure cycle V / $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates.

cycle alterations and to associate some AE response characteristics to the particular composite structure.

As regards 0° laminates, it is evident from figs. 1 and 2 that the difference in cure cycle determines, with a high degree of reproducibility, a marked different AE response: cure cycle II as compared to cure cycle I is characterized by a much lower activity in terms of N_{ta} and N_{te} , a consistently higher ratio N_{te}/N_{ta} and an absolute absence of high intensity bursts.

The same observations can be made concerning $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates cured with cycle I and II (figs. 3, 4, and 5): cure cycle II is again characterized by lower global activity, higher ratio N_{te}/N_{ta} and absence of bursts. In the case of cure cycle I, though, the AE response was not univocally reproducible. The presence of two test "groups", exemplified by figs. 3 and 4, with qualitatively similar but quantitatively different AE responses introduces a degree of uncertainty, especially in the reliability of parameters like N_{ta} and N_{te} . It is interesting to note that the ratio N_{te}/N_{ta} is the same for both groups: this suggests a better correspondence of the latter parameter to material rupture modes, as was noticed also in (6).

The comparison of cure cycles II and IV typical AE responses ($\pm 45^\circ$ laminates) allows for some interesting considerations: for both cure cycles it may be noticed an absolute absence of bursts, contrarily to what was observed for cure cycle I ($\pm 45^\circ$ and 0° laminates). Cure cycle II and IV have in common a fast heat-up phase (tab. I); on the other hand cure cycle I is characterized by a very slow heat-up. It seems therefore that the presence of bursts may be associated with the resin cure properties determining different fracture behaviours. A low heat-up rate generates a smaller number of reticulation sites, as compared to a high heat-up rate, and consequently a less uniform reticulation degree in the resin gel state. Such resin structure cannot but represent a rather unstable equilibrium condition that should react, in terms of AE, "explosively" (burst activity) to any external load application.

Cure cycle IV differs from cure cycle II only for the late pressure application (tab. I) that induces a higher porosity content in the laminate (tab. II). Porosity seems to influence critically the AE response both of $\pm 45^\circ$ and 0° lamina

cure cycle characteristic parameters (2).

AE testing, as was expected from the results of (5), proves capable of clearly discriminating the two different kinds of laminates (0° and $\pm 45^\circ$) both through simple quantitative parameters (N_{ta} , N_{te} , N_{te}/N_{ta}) and through its pattern characteristics. We shall not dwell on this aspect of the results as it was not the main scope of the testing programme. What seems more interesting, examining tab. II and figs. 2 - 8, is the concrete possibility offered by AE detection both to discriminate cure

tes: it apparently provokes a stronger activity both in terms of ring-down counts and event counts (tab. II). The only exceptions are given by the second "group" of cure cycle I / $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates displaying also a problem of reproducibility and certainly needing further testing, and cure cycle V / $\pm 45^\circ$ samples. In the latter case, though, it must be considered that the low ultimate stress of these samples involves a limited test duration; by calculating ratios N_{ta} / σ_{ult} and N_{te} / σ_{ult} , it can be shown that the cure cycle V samples have the highest ring-down and event counts per unit of strength (tab. II). It can therefore be maintained that cure cycle V displays both the highest porosity and the highest AE activity: this confirms the general trend for which higher porosity yields stronger AE.

Porosity influences also ratio N_{te} / N_{ta} : from table II it can be seen that porous laminates are characterized by a lower percentage of events at failure.

The influence of porosity on the AE response can be easily explained by the stress concentration effect due to the presence of voids that inevitably favour crack initiation and other "noisy" fracture modes producing a high number of high amplitude AE events (i.e. high N_{ta} , high N_{te} and low N_{te} / N_{ta}). This hypothesis is also supported by the fact that porous samples start emitting notably earlier, in terms of % of u.s., than non porous ones (cure cycle II).

CONCLUSIONS

From the above considerations the following conclusions can be drawn:

- AE analysis offers the possibility to detect unacceptable porosity contents by setting a limit, different from each kind of laminate, to the AE parameters, N_{ta} , N_{te} and N_{te} / N_{ta} . The latter parameter proved reliable for this purpose also in the only case where the AE pattern was not univocally reproduced in all tests (cure cycle I / $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates).
- AE seems also capable to identify non-uniformity in the resin reticulation degree. As this resin structural property influences critically the resin water sorption and consequently the composite environment resistance (7), AE proves very interesting for material evaluation testing of composite structures, considering that microscopic examinations do not seem to display the same capability (2).

These two points naturally suggest the possibility to detect, through an appropriate AE testing technique, accidental non conformities to the fabrication cycle specifications of GFRP composite components in a non destructive proof testing procedure. This is what the authors propose to verify in the course of the present research programme.

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